

THE ACTION OF HEXAMETHYLENETETRAMINE ON PHENOLS AND
THE METHYL ESTERS OF PHENOLCARBOXYLIC ACIDS. PART VI.
THE SYNTHESIS AND STUDY OF THE ARYLAMIDES OF
1-FORMYL-2-HYDROXY-3-NAPHTHOIC ACID

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The formylation of the anilide, β -naphthylamides and *m*-nitroanilide of 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid by hexamethylenetetramine has been studied. The resulting products have been subjected to Knoevenagel's, Perkin's and Clemmensen's reactions.

In an attempt to formylate β -naphthol with hexamethylenetetramine, Duff and Bills (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1305) obtained 1:1'-methylene-2:2'-dinaphthol and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde. They also formylated salicylic acid to 3- and 5-aldehydosalicylic acids (*ibid.* 1932, 1987). Desai, Radha and Shah (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1946, 23A, 182) were able to prepare methyl 1-formyl-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoate from methyl 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoate by the same method. The same reaction has now been applied to some arylamides of 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid, as these are now commercially available. Thus, naphthol AS or the anilide of 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid gave readily the anilide of 1-formyl-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid. That the formylation took place in position-1 was shown by the fact that the resulting compound did not couple with diazo salts. It gave readily the 4-nitrophenylhydrazone, 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone and the semicarbazone. The *ortho*-position of the formyl and hydroxyl groups was further shown by their Knoevenagel condensation with malonic and acetoacetic esters which gave 3-carbethoxy-10-anilido- β -naphtha- α -pyrone and 3-acetyl-10-anilido- β -naphtha- α -pyrone. Similarly Perkin's reaction gave 10-anilido- β -naphtha- α -pyrone. The Clemmensen reduction furnished different results with the use of methyl alcohol and acetic acid as solvents. A good yield of the anilide of 1-methyl-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid was obtained in presence of methyl alcohol, while a sticky substance, which could not be crystallised, was obtained in presence of acetic acid. Similar anomaly was observed by Desai, Radha and Shah (*loc. cit.*) in the case of methyl 1-formyl-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoate. The formylation of α -naphthylamide, β -naphthylamide and *m*-nitroanilide of 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid was similarly studied and the various reactions of the formyl derivatives were examined. We are also extending these reactions to the other members of the naphthol AS series.

2-Hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid (or its derivatives), formylation of which by hexamethylenetetramine is described herein, has also been previously formylated by use of the standard Reimer and Tiemann's reaction (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1898, II, 836).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Formylation of the Anilide of 2-Hydroxy-3-naphthoic Acid; Formation of the Anilide of 1-Formyl-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic Acid.—The anilide (10 g.) was slowly added to a solution of hexamethylenetetramine (20 g.) in glacial acetic acid (100 c.c.) with shaking and heated on a sand-bath under reflux for 6 hours. After the addition of HCl (dil., 20 c.c.), the heating of the mixture was continued for 1 hour more and the solution poured into a large excess of water. The solid separating was filtered, washed and crystallised from alcohol in small, lustrous, yellow needles, m.p. 138°, yield 60%. Its alcoholic solution gave a reddish brown coloration with ferric chloride. The substance did not couple with diazo salts, proving the position-1 of the formyl group. (Found: C, 73.9; H, 4.1; N, 4.5. $C_{18}H_{13}O_3N$ requires C, 74.2; H, 4.8; N, 4.4%).

The *p*-nitrophenylhydrazone was prepared by heating the mixture of the above formyl compound (0.3 g.), *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine (0.3 g.) and glacial acetic acid (15 c.c.) for 3 hours. The orange-red solid crystallised out from glacial acetic acid in plates, m.p. 176°. (Found: N, 12.8. $C_{21}H_{18}O_4N_2$ requires N, 13.1%).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was crystallised from acetic acid in orange-red needles, m.p. 245°. (Found: N, 14.3. $C_{24}H_{17}O_6N_4$ requires N, 14.6%).

The semicarbazone was crystallised from alcohol in pale yellow, small needles, m.p. 254°. (Found: N, 16.0. $C_{19}H_{18}O_3N_3$ requires N, 16.2%).

Condensation of the Formylhydroxyanilide with Acetoacetic Ester: Formation of 3-Acetyl-10-anilido- β -naphtha- α -pyrone—To a solution of the hydroxyformyl derivative (0.5 g.) in pyridine (15 c.c.) were added ethyl acetoacetate (0.6 g.) and traces of piperidine (5 drops). After keeping the mixture at room temperature overnight, it was heated on a water-bath for 2 hours and poured into HCl (dilute, 1:1). The solid was crystallised from alcohol in brown needles, m.p. 178°. Its alcoholic solution did not give any coloration with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 73.3; H, 4.0; N, 3.7. $C_{22}H_{19}O_4N$ requires C, 73.9; H, 4.2; N, 3.9%).

Condensation with Diethyl Malonate: Formation of 3-Carboxy-10-anilido- β -naphtha- α -pyrone—A mixture of the hydroxyformyl compound (0.9 g.), ethyl malonate (1 g.), pyridine (25 c.c.) and piperidine (5 drops) was heated on a water-bath for 3 hours, after being kept at the room temperature for 24 hours. The solid separating after adding the mixture to dilute hydrochloric acid (1:1) was crystallised from alcohol in reddish microcrystals, m.p. 234°. Its alcoholic solution gave negative ferric chloride test. (Found: C, 71.0; H, 4.2; N, 3.2. $C_{23}H_{17}O_5N$ requires C, 71.3; H, 4.4; N, 3.5%).

Perkin's Reaction on the Hydroxyformyl Derivative: Formation of 10-Anilido- β -naphtha- α -pyrone—A mixture of the hydroxyformyl derivative (1 g.), acetic anhydride (15 c.c.) and anhydrous sodium acetate (2 g.) was heated on a sand-bath for 6 hours. The mixture was added to water and the solid was crystallised from alcohol in small needles, m.p. 161°. (Found: C, 76.5; H, 4.0; N, 4.3. $C_{20}H_{15}O_3N$ requires C, 76.2; H, 4.1; N, 4.4%).

Clemmensen's Reduction of the Hydroxyformyl Derivative: Formation of Anilide of 1-Methyl-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic Acid.—The anilide of 1-formyl-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid (2 g.), dissolved in methyl alcohol (50 c.c.), was gradually added to amalgamated zinc dust (30 g.) and HCl (dil., 1:1, 50 c.c.), and heated on a sand-bath under reflux. Methyl alcohol was removed from the hot filtered liquid and the solution extracted with ether. The solid recovered from ether was crystallised from alcohol in brown needles, m.p. 181°. Its alcoholic solution gave a blue coloration with ferric chloride and negative tests with aldehydic reagents. (Found: C, 77.3; H, 5.2; N, 4.7. $C_{18}H_{15}O_2N$ requires C, 77.7; H, 5.4; N, 5.0%).

Formylation of α -Naphthylamide of 2-Hydroxy-3-naphthoic Acid: Formation of α -Naphthylamide of 1-Formyl-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic Acid.—The formylation was carried out as usual using α -naphthylamide of 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid (12 g.) and hexamethylenetetramine (24 g.) in glacial acetic acid (100 c.c.) and the α -naphthylamide was crystallised from alcohol in brown needles, m.p. 192°, yield 60%. Its alcoholic solution gave a reddish brown coloration with ferric chloride. It did not couple with diazo salts. (Found: C, 77.9; H, 4.8; N, 4.9. $C_{22}H_{15}O_3N$ requires C, 77.3; H, 4.4; N, 4.1%).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in orange needles, m.p. 226°. (Found: N, 13.5. $C_{28}H_{18}O_6N_6$ requires N, 13.4%).

The semicarbazone was crystallised from alcohol in small plates, m.p. 332-33°. (Found: N, 13.9. $C_{23}H_{18}O_3N_4$ requires N, 14.1%).

3-Acetyl-10- α -naphthylamido- β -naphtho- α -pyrone, obtained from the hydroxyformyl compound (0.5 g.) and acetoacetic ester (0.6 g.) as usual, was crystallised from alcohol in small yellowish red needles, m.p. 247°. Its alcoholic solution gave negative tests with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 76.1; H, 4.1; N, 3.7. $C_{25}H_{17}O_4N$ requires C, 76.6; H, 4.2; N, 3.4%).

3-Carboxy-10- α -naphthylamido- β -naphtho- α -pyrone was obtained as usual from the formyl compound (1 g.) and ethyl malonate (1 g.) and it was crystallised from dilute alcohol in orange needles, m.p. 241°. (Found: C, 74.4; H, 4.2; N, 3.5. $C_{27}H_{19}O_5N$ requires C, 74.1; H, 4.3; N, 3.2%).

10-Naphthylamido- β -naphtho- α -pyrone, obtained from the hydroxyformyl compound (1 g.) by Perkin's reaction as usual, was crystallised from alcohol in small brown needles, m.p. 207°. (Found: C, 79.0; H, 4.0; N, 4.1. $C_{24}H_{15}O_3N$ requires C, 78.8; H, 4.1; N, 3.8%).

α -Naphthylamide of 1-methyl-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid was obtained by the Clemmensen reduction of the hydroxyformyl compound and was crystallised from alcohol in brown needles, m.p. 158°. Its alcoholic solution gave a blue coloration with ferric chloride and did not react with aldehydic reagents. (Found: C, 80.5; H, 5.5; N, 4.5. $C_{22}H_{17}O_2N$ requires C, 80.1; H, 5.2; N, 4.2%).

Formylation of β -Naphthylamide of 2-Hydroxy-3-naphthoic Acid: Formation of β -Naphthylamide of 1-Formyl-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic Acid.—The formylation was carried

out as usual using the amide (12 g.), hexamethylenetetramine (24 g.) and glacial acetic acid (100 c.c.). The β -naphthylamide was crystallised from acetic acid in lustrous, yellow plates, m.p. 225° , yield 60%. Its alcoholic solution gave a reddish coloration with ferric chloride. Its alkaline solution did not couple with diazo salts. (Found: C, 77.6; H, 4.3; N, 4.3. $C_{22}H_{15}O_2N$ requires C, 77.3; H, 4.4; N, 4.1%).

The *p*-nitrophenylhydrazone was crystallised from acetic acid in small orange plates, m.p. 180° . (Found: N, 11.5. $C_{16}H_{10}O_4N_2$ requires N, 11.8%).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was obtained as a chocolate compound in a powder form, m.p. 196° . (Found: N, 13.1. $C_{20}H_{10}O_6N_4$ requires N, 13.5%).

The semicarbazone was crystallised from alcohol in small orange plates, m.p. 250° . (Found: N, 14.2. $C_{23}H_{18}O_2N_4$ requires N, 14.1%).

The 3-acetyl-10- β -naphthylamido- β -naphtha-2-pyrone, prepared in the usual manner from the hydroxyformyl derivative (0.5 g.) and acetoacetic ester (0.6 g.), was crystallised from alcohol in brown needles, m.p. 167° . Its alcoholic solution did not give any coloration with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 76.5; H, 4.1; N, 3.8. $C_{28}H_{17}O_4N$ requires C, 76.6; H, 4.2; N, 3.4%).

10- β -Naphthylamido- β -naphtha-2-pyrone was obtained by heating the hydroxyformyl derivative (1 g.) with acetic anhydride (15 c.c.) and sodium acetate (2 g.) as usual. It was crystallised from alcohol in small brown needles, m.p. 179° . (Found: C, 79.1; H, 3.9; N, 4.2. $C_{27}H_{17}O_2N$ requires C, 78.8; H, 4.1; N, 3.8%).

β -Naphthylamide of 1-methyl-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid was obtained by the Clemmensen reduction of the hydroxyformyl derivative and was crystallised from alcohol in small pink needles, m.p. 110° . Its alcoholic solution gave a blue coloration with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 80.8; H, 5.2; N, 4.5. $C_{23}H_{17}O_2N$ requires C, 80.6; H, 5.4; N, 4.2%).

Formylation of m-Nitroanilide of 2-Hydroxy-3-naphthoic Acid: Formation of 3-Nitroanilide of 1-Formyl-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic Acid.—The formylation was done as usual using the anilide (12 g.), hexamethylenetetramine (24 g.) and glacial acetic acid (100 c.c.). The product was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in small yellow plates, m.p. 206° , yield 60%. Its alcoholic solution gave a reddish brown coloration with ferric chloride. Its alkaline solution did not couple with diazo salts. (Found: C, 64.3; H, 3.6; N, 8.1. $C_{18}H_{12}O_3N_2$ requires C, 64.1; H, 3.7; N, 8.3%).

The *p*-nitrophenylhydrazone was crystallised from alcohol in small orange plates, m.p. 273° . (Found: N, 14.6. $C_{24}H_{17}O_4N_2$ requires N, 14.8%).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was crystallised from alcohol in orange plates, m.p. 285° . (Found: N, 16.4. $C_{24}H_{16}O_6N_4$ requires N, 16.2%).

The semicarbazone was crystallised from alcohol in small yellow needles, m.p. 340° . (Found: N, 18.1. $C_{19}H_{16}O_2N_4$ requires N, 17.8%).

3-Acetyl-10-*m*-nitroanilido- β -naphtha-2-pyrone was prepared from the hydroxyformyl derivative (0.5 g.) and acetoacetic ester (0.6 g.) as usual and it was crystallised from alcohol in brown needles, m.p. 171° . (Found: C, 65.7; H, 3.7; N, 7.1. $C_{27}H_{14}O_6N_2$ requires C, 65.6; H, 3.5; N, 6.9%).

3-Carbethoxy-10-m-nitroanilido- β -naphtha-a-pyrone was prepared from the hydroxyformyl compound (1 g.) and malonic ester (1 c.c.) as usual. It was crystallised from alcohol in fine needles, m.p. 135°. (Found: C, 63.7; H, 3.8; N, 6.6. $C_{23}H_{16}O_7N_2$ requires C, 63.9; H, 3.6; N, 6.3%).

10-m-Nitroanilido- β -naphtha-a-pyrone, obtained by the Perkin reaction on the hydroxyformyl derivative, was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in fine needles, m.p. 162°. (Found: C, 66.2; H, 3.4; N, 7.8. $C_{20}H_{13}O_5N_2$ requires C, 66.9; H, 3.7; N, 7.5%).

m-Nitroanilide of 1-methyl-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid was obtained by the Clemmensen reduction of the hydroxyformyl compound as usual and it was crystallised from alcohol in small brown needles, m.p. 85°. It gave a blue coloration with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 67.4; H, 4.3; N, 8.8. $C_{18}H_{14}O_4N_2$ requires C, 67.0; H, 4.1; N, 8.4%). •

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